

Preparation of Anils from *p*-Bromophenylglyoxal Hydrate and Aromatic Amines

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A number of new anils prepared from phenylglyoxal, β -naphthylglyoxal hydrates and aromatic amino compounds have been reported earlier.¹⁻³ A few more anils, from *p*-bromophenylglyoxalhydrate and various aromatic amines, have been synthesised to add to our existing knowledge of this type of compounds. The reaction products were characterised from their *p*-nitrophenylhydrazones, 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazones, semicarbazones and oximes.

p-Bromophenylglyoxalhydrate was synthesised by oxidising *p*-bromoacetophenone with selenium dioxide⁴. Equimolar quantities of *p*-bromophenylglyoxalhydrate and corresponding amines in 95% ethanol were refluxed on a water bath. The solid products obtained on cooling were separated and crystallised from hot alcohol. These anils were found to be soluble in methanol, acetone, acetonitrile, benzene, toluene but were practically insoluble in water and petroleum ether. They are listed in Table 1.

TABLE I

Anils derived from p-bromophenylglyoxal hydrate and aromatic amines.

Anil	Colour	Formula	M.P. °C	Yield %	Nitrogen %	
					Calcd.	Found
R-aniline	Light Yellow	C ₁₄ H ₁₀ ONBr	60-61	78.21	4.86	4.81
R- <i>o</i> -toluidine	Brown	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ONBr	76-77	56.32	4.63	4.59
R- <i>m</i> -toluidine	Brown	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ONBr	74-75	52.35	4.63	4.62
R- <i>γ</i> -toluidine	Yellow	C ₁₅ H ₁₂ ONBr	86-87	64.52	4.63	4.57
R- <i>o</i> -chloroaniline	Brown	C ₁₄ H ₉ ONClBr	Gummy	—	4.34	—
R- <i>m</i> -chloroaniline	Dark Brown	C ₁₄ H ₉ ONClBr	82-83	56.52	4.34	4.29
R- <i>p</i> -chloroaniline	Black	C ₁₄ H ₉ ONClBr	65-66	73.42	4.34	4.31
R-sulphanilamide	Brown	C ₁₄ H ₁₁ O ₃ N ₂ SBr	112-113	68.23	7.63	7.60

R = (Br-C₆H₄-CO-CH = *p*-bromophenacylidene radical)

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TABLE II
Characteristics of the derivatives of the anils.

Anil	<i>p</i> -Nitrophenylhydrazones			2, 4-Dinitrophenylhydrazones			Semicarbazones			Oximes		
	M.P. °C	Nitrogen % Calcd.	Nitrogen % Found	M.P. °C	Nitrogen % Calcd.	Nitrogen % Found	M.P. °C	Nitrogen % Calcd.	Nitrogen % Found	M.P. °C	Nitrogen % Calcd.	Nitrogen % Found
R-aniline	267-268	13.24	13.21	258-260	14.95	14.86	231-232	16.24	16.18	155-156	9.25	9.12
R- <i>o</i> -toluidine	290-291	12.86	12.45	250-251	14.52	14.32	142-143	15.61	16.59	Gummy	8.83	—
R- <i>m</i> -toluidine	250-251	12.86	12.58	245-247	14.52	14.42	183-184	15.61	15.62	Gummy	8.83	—
R- <i>p</i> -toluidine	281-282	12.86	12.67	286-288	14.52	14.48	207-209	15.61	15.44	128-129	8.83	8.79
R- <i>o</i> -chloroaniline	231-233	12.22	12.13	246-248	13.90	13.82	196-197	14.74	14.68	193-195	8.28	8.23
R- <i>m</i> -chloroaniline	221-223	12.22	12.05	215-217	13.90	13.75	238-239	14.74	14.72	Gummy	8.28	—
R- <i>p</i> -chloroaniline	219-220	12.22	12.18	284-285	13.90	13.64	232-234	14.74	14.69	143-144	8.28	8.25
R-sulphanilamide	282-284	13.94	13.84	272-274	12.73	12.68	240-241	16.51	16.48	Gummy	11.00 m	—

R = (Br-C₆H₄-CO-CH = *p*-bromophenacylidene radical)

TABLE III
Infrared stretching frequencies of the functional groups of some of the anils and their derivatives cm^{-1} .

No.	Structural Formulae	C=O	-CH=N	C-NO ₂	-NH	-OH	I : 4	Disubstituted group
1.	$\text{Br}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$	1690	1600	—	—	—	860	
2.	$\text{Br}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{Cl}(p)$	1690	1590	—	—	—	815	
3.	$\text{Br}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{CH}_3(m)$	1700	1600	—	—	—	850	
4.	$\text{Br}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\overset{\text{O}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$	—	1585, 1610	1420, 1490	3280	—	830	
5.	$\text{Br}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\overset{\text{D}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{CH}_3(o)$	—	1580, 1600	1415, 1490	3280	—	830	
6.	$\text{Br}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\overset{\text{D}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{Cl}(p)$	—	1525, 1600	1425, 1500	3440	—	830	
7.	$\text{Br}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\overset{\text{D}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{SO}_2\text{NH}_2$	—	1550, 1600	1450, 1520	3500	—	830	
8.	$\text{Br}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\overset{\text{P}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{SO}_2\text{NH}_2$	—	1550, 1590	1490	3260	—	835	
9.	$\text{Br}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\overset{\text{P}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{Cl}(o)$	—	1550, 1590	1420	3280	—	830	
10.	$\text{Br}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\overset{\text{P}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{Cl}(p)$	—	1540, 1590	1490	3260	—	830	
11.	$\text{Br}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\overset{\text{P}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}=\text{N}-3''_o\text{H}_4-\text{SO}_2\text{NH}_2$	1700	1600	—	3440	—	—	
12.	$\text{Br}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\overset{\text{S}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_5$	1730	1650	—	3500	—	—	
13.	$\text{Br}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\overset{\text{S}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{Cl}(p)$	1700	1605	—	3400	—	840	
14.	$\text{Br}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\overset{\text{S}}{\parallel}{\text{C}}-\text{CH}=\text{N}-\text{C}_6\text{H}_4-\text{CH}_3(p)$ N-OH	—	1600	—	—	3275	830	

D = 2, 4-dinitrophenylhydrazone unit
P = *p* nitrophenylhydrazone unit
S = semicarbazone unit.

Derivatives of the Anils : *p*-Nitrophenylhydrazones, 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones semicarbazones and oximes were prepared by the usual methods and were obtained almost in theoretical yield. *p*-Nitrophenylhydrazones and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones were crystallised from nitrobenzene. Semicarbazones and oximes were, however, crystallised from ethanol. The oximes of *p*-bromophenacylidene-*o*-, *m*-toluidines and *m*-, *p*-chloroanilines afforded a gummy mass which could not, however, be crystallised. The characteristics of these anils are recorded in Table II.

*I.R. Spectral Studies*⁵ : The infra-red spectra of some of the anils synthesised and their derivatives were recorded in solid state using KBr technique with a view to ascertaining the presence of different functional groups. Perkin-Elmer 521 and Beckmann I.R.-4 infracord were employed for this purpose. The stretching frequencies of some of the groups are listed in Table III.

DISCUSSION

Anils : The stretching frequencies of an aryl ketone lie between 1700–1680 cm^{-1} and that of $-\text{CH}=\text{N}$ (azomethine group) between 1630–1613 cm^{-1} . From the spectra of these anils, it is quite evident that the above groups are present in their molecules since sharp peaks around 1700 cm^{-1} and 1600 cm^{-1} exist. However, lowering of frequency in some compounds might be due to such effects as I, M, steric hindrance and conjugation etc.

p-Nitro- and 2,4-dinitrophenylhydrazones : Aromatic nitro compounds show a band in the range of 1560–1350 cm^{-1} due to C-NO₂ group. The nitro derivatives also show this peak besides the normal peaks for C=O and CH=N. However, in disubstituted nitro compounds multiple frequencies are observed. This is evident from the stretching frequency of the compounds 4–11. Here too slight deviation in values may be attributed to I, M and steric effects.

>NH group shows a characteristic frequency between 3400–3000 cm^{-1} . Since the hydrazones are known to exhibit a peak around this range, the presence of >NH group in such type of compounds is confirmed.

In the sulphanilamide derivative a peak at 1080 cm^{-1} is observed which may be due to S=O in SO₂NH₂ grouping. Other peaks, viz., those in the range of 690–645 cm^{-1} and 750–700 cm^{-1} are due to C-Br and C-Cl linkages respectively.

Semicarbazones : Apart from CH=N, >NH peaks in such type of compounds, NH₂ peak of CONH₂ group is diagonalisable above 3000 cm^{-1} . Besides this, a peak obtained around 3200 cm^{-1} is characteristic of a C-CH₃ grouping in some of these compounds.

Oximes : -OH and >C=N groups are also present in these compounds due to oximino C=N-OH linkage. This is evident from the OH frequency values around 3200 cm^{-1} .

5. (a) C. N. R. Rao, "Chemical applications of Infra-red spectroscopy.", 1963, Academic Press, New York and London.

(b) K. Nakanishi, "Infra-red Absorption Spectroscopy", 1962, Holden-Day-Inc. San Francisco.

Most of these compounds are *p*-disubstituted derivatives whose frequency lies in the range of 840-820 cm^{-1} .

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